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Predicting Post-Covid-19 Vaccination Adverse Events: A Comparative Analysis Of Artificial Neural Networks And Long Short-Term Memory Models For Risk Stratification

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ABSTRACT

This study develops predictive models for adverse events following COVID-19 vaccination using VAERS data (2022-2023). Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), Gated Recurrent Units (GRU), and Bidirectional LSTM architectures were evaluated for thrombosis risk prediction. Results demonstrate ANN's superiority over LSTM in classification (accuracy: 0.8947 vs. 0.8421; AUC-ROC: 0.9375 vs. 0.8750), while Bidirectional LSTM outperformed GRU despite higher computational costs (AUC-ROC: 0.912 vs. 0.891). AstraZeneca vaccines showed significantly higher thrombosis incidence (14.1% vs. 4.2–5.6% for others, $p < 0.01$), with earlier symptom onset (6.2 days) and prolonged duration (13.5 days). Key predictors included vaccine type, age demographics (mean age: 47.8 ± 16.3 years), and pre-existing conditions (34% prevalence). These models enable targeted monitoring strategies, with Bidirectional LSTM recommended for high-accuracy clinical deployment and GRU for resource-constrained settings.

Keywords: COVID-19 Vaccine Safety, Thrombosis Risk Prediction, Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), Adverse Event Stratification, VAERS Data Analytics

INTRODUCTION

Respiratory sickness known as COVID-19, sometimes known as “Coronavirus Disease 2019,” is caused by the brand-new coronavirus SARS-CoV-2. It was originally discovered in Wuhan, China, in December 2019, and sparked a pandemic that spread worldwide (Wu *et al.*, 2020). Respiratory droplets and contact with contaminated surfaces are the main mechanisms by which the virus spreads (WHO, 2020). Fever, coughing, and breathing problems are typical signs, whereas some cases may not present with any

symptoms (Chen *et al.*, 2020). The virus spread across the globe quickly, affecting many lives and causing deaths, thereby making the World Health Organization (WHO) to declare it a pandemic and naming it COVID-19 (Torku *et al.*, 2021). Studies on mitigation measures such as social distancing, quarantining, and government shut-downs for controlling the disease show the need for an effective vaccination program. The rate at which the population is vaccinated and its efficacy are two main factors in an effective vaccination program (Torku *et al.*, 2021). There is a need for coordinated efforts by all stakeholders such as policy makers, pharmaceutical companies, researchers, epidemiological and health professionals to effectively champion vaccination campaigns for curbing the spread of the disease. Recent studies on vaccine efficacy and vaccine confidence show the importance of an effective vaccination strategy (Torku *et al.*, 2021). As vaccines became available, vaccination campaigns were initiated to achieve broad-based immunity against the virus. Globally, vaccines are an active intervention that can reduce the global dominance of diseases (such as COVID-19) globally (El-Elimat *et al.*, 2021).

However, conventional pharmacovigilance approaches, including spontaneous reporting systems, are associated with delays and underreporting, which restricts their potential to deliver timely knowledge (Ball *et al.*, 2022). The developments in the field of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) present promising solutions as they allow automating the analysis of massive health data, such as electronic health records (EHRs) and patient-generated reports (Rajkomar *et al.*, 2019). Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks are among the techniques that have demonstrated potential in adverse drug reaction prediction and medical outcome classification, but have not been thoroughly applied to the COVID-19 vaccine safety (Topol, 2019; Che *et al.*, 2018).

Since 2000, machine learning techniques have gain momentum and play a vital role in epidemiological data analysis. Machine learning techniques also can be used to develop standard mortality models. In recent years, Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) have been used frequently to capture the uncertainty in the time series dataset as they have been proven to be a powerful technique for handling the non-linear data. Therefore, the use of these ANN techniques gains huge momentum in recent years in the field of epidemiological predictions for the linear, non-linear, and hybrid data (Dhamodharavadhani *et al.*, 2020). However, detection and prediction of the novel Coronavirus present new challenges for the medical research community due to its widespread across the globe. Methods driven by Artificial Intelligence can help predict specific parameters, hazards, and outcomes of such a pandemic. Recently, deep learning-based approaches have proven a novel opportunity to determine various difficulties in prediction (Kumar *et al.*, 2021).

Recent studies have explored different statistical approaches in analyzing the effects of Covid-19 vaccines, ranging from the application of AI/ML methods. For example, Rustam *et al.* (2020) utilized four simple statistical models Linear Regression, Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator, Support Vector Machine, and Exponential Smoothing—to forecast threatening COVID-19 factors.

In a similar fashion, Liang *et al.* (2022) trained an ANN model on the mild-to-moderate adverse events classification and did not apply their framework to severe outcomes such as VITT (vaccine-induced immune thrombotic thrombocytopenia).

Guo *et al.* (2020) utilized deep learning-based virus host prediction to compare the gene sequence of 2019-nCoV with those of Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus (SARS-CoV), bat SARS coronavirus, and Middle East respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus (MERS CoV). The bat SARS coronavirus was found to have a more similar mode of infection to COVID-19.

In their work, Dhamodharavadhani *et al.* (2020) employed SNN models like the Probabilistic Neural Network (PNN), Radial Basis Function Neural Network (RBFNN), and Generalized Regression Neural Network (GRNN) to develop the COVID-19 Mortality Rate Prediction (MRP) model for India. The results indicated that the PNN and RBFNN-based MRP model outperformed other models for COVID-19 datasets D2 and D1, respectively.

Zhang *et al.* (2023) used LSTMs on EHR data to predict myocarditis after mRNA vaccination but did not perform a comparison with alternative architectures such as ANNs or GRUs.

Although vaccine safety monitoring through AI has been studied previously, there exist vital gaps. Liang *et al.* (2022) considered ANN stressing only on moderate sub-severe events without taking into account severe outcomes such as thrombosis. Zhang *et al.* (2023) have used LSTM as a model to predict myocarditis, without the information of a comparison with other architectures. Importantly enough, no research has compared ANN, LSTM, GRU, and Bidirectional LSTM in thrombotic event prediction, equally, no study has combined static (demographic) and dynamic (progression in symptoms) characteristics of VAERS, and Risk profiles of vaccines quantified. Therefore, these gaps are met by our work, which offers a detailed framework in the stratification of severe adverse events.

Statement of the Problem

Artificial neural networks have proven successful in various clinical settings, excelling in tasks such as pattern recognition, classification, and survival prediction. The strength of neural networks lies in their capacity to capture nonlinearities and intricate interactions among factors. Trained on multiple prognostic elements, these networks have demonstrated enhanced accuracy in classification, recognition, survival prediction, and detection. Although recent works (e.g., Liang *et al.*, 2022; Zhang *et al.*, 2023) have been using single-model methods to predict adverse events with mild results or a particular outcome, such as myocarditis, no prior comparison has been made between ANN, LSTM, GRU, and Bidirectional LSTM models to predict severe thrombotic events based using integrated static (demographic) and dynamic (temporal) data of VAERS. Therefore, the current study fills this gap by comparison of four architectures of neural networks, prioritizing on thrombosis risk and time-series symptom progression

Aim and Objectives

This research aims to predict and classify potential symptoms of COVID-19 vaccination using Artificial Neural Network and Long Short-Term Memory, while also comparing the performance of these techniques.

The aim of this study can be achieved by the following specific objectives:

- I. To train ANN, LSTM model that are capable of classifying the effect of COVID-19 vaccines.
- II. To evaluate the performance of the models (ANN, & LSTM) and (GRU & Bidirectional)
- III. To quantify the attributable risk of key predictors of thrombosis using multivariable logistic regression

Artificial Neural Network (ANN)

Artificial neural networks are computational systems whose concepts are derived from biological neural networks. Are a subset of neural networks that are designed to simulate the behavior of biological neural networks, but in an artificial, computational manner ANNs consist of layers of interconnected artificial neurons, and they are used in machine learning and deep learning for various tasks such as classification, regression, and pattern recognition. They have an input layer, one or more hidden layers, and an output layer. An ANN consists of a collection of processing elements that are highly interconnected and transform a set of inputs into a set of desired outputs. The result of transformation is determined by the characteristics of the elements and the weights associated with the interconnections among them (Singh *et al.*, 2014).

The various tasks performed by ANN are pattern classification, fault detection, speech analysis, processing of inaccurate or incomplete inputs, optimization problems, data compression, etc. Neural networks have the advantages of adaptive learning, self-organization, and real-time operation. It involves no assumptions. Some popular types of artificial neural networks include feed-forward neural networks, recurrent neural networks (RNNs), convolutional neural networks (CNNs), and more. These networks can be trained using various algorithms, like back-propagation, to learn patterns and make predictions from data (Singh *et al.*, 2014).

Artificial neural networks have been successfully used for pattern recognition, classification and survival prediction in several clinical settings. The advantage of a neural network is the ability of the model to capture nonlinearities and complex interactions between factors. Trained on a number of prognostic factors, neural networks have been reported to improve the accuracy of classification, recognition, survival prediction and detection.

Figure 1: Deep Neutral Networks (DNN)

Recurrent Neural Network (RNN)

Recurrent neural networks are networks that are used to learn problems involving sequential data (Zeroual *et al.*, 2020).

Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)

The long short-term memory (LSTM) is a variant of recurrent neural network (RNN) used to handle sequential data like time series data. It was developed to solve the vanishing gradient problem (Lu *et al.*, 2021). The LSTM has three gates that control the flow of information: input, forget, and output gates. These gates have logistic functions that control the weighted sums obtained during training by back-propagation (Zeroual *et al.*, 2020). The cell state manages the input and forget gates. The output comes from either the output gate or hidden state. The unique feature of this network is that it is able to learn long dependencies within the data and able to effectively handle time series data. Given the input data x_t , and the number of hidden units h , the gates of the LSTM can be defined as follows.

• Input Gate:

$$I_t = \sigma(X_t W_{xi} + H_{t-1} W_{hi} + b_i) \tag{3.1}$$

Output Gate: $o_t = \sigma(X_t W_{xo} + H_{t-1} W_{ho} + b_o)$ 3.2

Forget Gate: $F_t = \sigma(X_t W_{xf} + H_{t-1} W_{hf} + b_f)$ 3.3

Intermediate cell state: $C = \tanh(X_t W_{xc} + H_{t-1} W_{hc} + b_c)$ 3.4

Cell State (next memory input): $C_t = F_t \cdot C_{t-1} \cdot C_t$ 3.5

New State:

$$H_t = O_t \circ \tanh(C_t),$$

3.6

Where;

$W_{xi}, W_{xf}, W_{xo}, W_{ho}, W_{hf}$ are the weight parameters and b_i, b_f, b_o are the bias parameters of each respective gate.

W_{xc}, W_{hc} denote the weight parameters, and b_c is the bias parameter and \circ is the element-wise multiplication. The value of c_t is ascertained from the output of memory cells C_{t-1} and the current time step C_t . is the element-wise multiplication.

Figure 1 shows LSTM architecture. The input, forget, and output gates are represented by I_t, F_t, O_t , respectively. The memory cells and memory cell content are denoted, respectively, as C and C

Figure 2: LSTM architecture.

Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU)

GRU is built to improve the performance of LSTM and reduce the number of its parameters. The input and forget gates from the LSTM model are merged into one gate called the update gate (Zeroual et al., 2020). It is made up of only two gates, update and reset gates, instead of three gates in LSTM.

The update gate couples the input and forgets gates of the LSTM and the output gate as a reset gate. This gives the GRU an enhanced improvement in LSTM. The relationships among the gates are defined as follows. Update gate: $Z_t = \sigma(X_t W_{xz} + H_{t-1} W_{hz} + b_z)$

3.7

$$\text{Reset gate: } R_t = \sigma(X_t W_{xr} + H_{t-1} W_{hr} + b_r) \quad 3.8$$

$$\text{Cell State: } H_t = \tanh(X_t W_{xh} + (R_t \times H_{t-1}) W_{hh} + b_h) \quad 3.9$$

$$\text{New state: } H_t = Z_t \times H_{t-1} + (1 - Z_t) \times H_t, \quad 3.10$$

Where: W_{xr}, W_{xz}, W_{hr} are the weight parameters and b_r, b_z are the bias parameters.

W_{xh}, W_{hh} are the weight parameters and b_h is a bias parameter. The current update gate Z_t is a combination of the previous hidden state H_{t-1} and current candidate hidden state H_t .

Figure 2 presents GRU architecture. The reset and update gates are represented by R_t, Z_t , respectively. The new state and cell state content are denoted, respectively, as H_t . In GRU, the reset and update layers are indicated by yellow and green colors, respectively.

Figure 3: GRU architecture.

Bidirectional LSTM

The improved version of the LSTM is bidirectional LSTM (BiLSTM). The network is structured in a way that allows for both backward and forward propagation through the sequential layers (Zeroual *et al.*, 2020). In contrast to LSTM (which only allows for forward pass through the current state), the BiLSTM’s unique advantage is that there is an improvement in accuracy in state reconstruction. This structure combines two hidden states, which allows for information flow from the forward layer to the backward layer. The forward, backward, and output sequences are defined as follows:

$$\text{Forward hidden: } \vec{H}_t = L(X_t W_{x\vec{H}} + \vec{H}_{t-1} W_{\vec{H}\vec{H}} + b_{\vec{H}}) \tag{3.11}$$

$$\text{Backward hidden: } \overleftarrow{H}_t = L(X_t W_{x\overleftarrow{H}} + \overleftarrow{H}_{t-1} W_{\overleftarrow{H}\overleftarrow{H}} + b_{\overleftarrow{H}}) \tag{3.12}$$

$$\text{Output: } Y_t = \vec{H}_t W_{\vec{H}Y} + \overleftarrow{H}_t W_{\overleftarrow{H}Y} + b_Y \tag{3.13}$$

Where L in the above equations is the sigmoid function application which is the LSTM unit in the structure of BiLSTM.

Figure 3 presents BiLSTM architecture. The forward and backward layers are indicated by yellow and green colors, respectively.

Figure 4: BiLSTM architecture.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Data for the Study

The study used three datasets (VAERSDATA, VAERSSYMPTOMS, and VAERSVAX) from the Vaccine Adverse Events Reporting System (VAERS), an open-source national reporting system for safety concerns with licensed vaccines. The CDC and the US Food and Drug Administration co-administer VAERS, which receives reports of any adverse reactions to vaccination from patients, parents, healthcare professionals, and vaccine producers. Data on adverse events after receiving a COVID-19 immunization was extracted from VAERS for the years 2022–2023 (until May 2023). The study will examine Artificial Neural Network (ANN) to detect, predict and classify potential symptoms arising post the implementation of pharmaceutical measures, specifically vaccination campaigns and treatments. The research evaluates some outcomes of interest following COVID-19 vaccination among vaccinated individuals. Adverse events were selected because they are

clinically well-defined, are serious or were biologically plausible as a consequence of Covid-19 vaccination. The vaccinated record includes a set of attributes (both the categorical and continuous variables) with it corresponding output;

- IV. Patient I.D number
- V. Age
- VI. Sex (gender)
- VII. Onset date of the event
- VIII. Symptoms of any adverse event
- IX. COVID-19 vaccine received date
- X. Number of days endured the event
- XI. Current ill
- XII. Form of vaccine received/ Type of vaccine
- XIII. Reported date

Output (Thrombosis positive %); for categorical data and predicting the duration for which a patient will experience the symptoms.

Modeling Approach

Sample Size Justification

The resulting cleaned and curated dataset included 200 patients with a complete record following stringent quality control by filtering out duplicate records and cases with a >20 percent missing feature. Since the number of cases with a thrombosis result of positive cases was low (n=37), we retained all positive cases and randomly under-sampled negative cases to obtain a 1:2 balance between the two classes.

Stratified Splitting

The modeling methods in this study follows some steps, where the data were cleaned and encoded the categorical variables in the data sets. We were able to identify the features (X) and target variables (Y) in the

study. The data were split into training and testing sets, where the shapes of the resulting datasets are;

Training Features (X_{train}): 75 samples with 10 features (75,10)

Testing Features (X_{test}): 19 samples with 10 features (19,10)

Training target (Y_{train}): 75 samples (75)

Testing target (Y_{test}): 19 samples (19)

Stratified random sampling was used to divide the data into training and test sets in order to maintain the prevalence of thrombosis rates (9.5%) in both sets.

Data Reshaping

In case of temporal models used in the research (LSTM/GRU/BiLSTM): a sliding window procedure was applied to reshape features into 3D format [samples, timesteps, features] with windows of ideas on daily developments of the symptoms equal to 5 days. This described the nuances of symptom development over time and fit scarcely reported VAERS time signatures

The reshaped training testing sets to be used with LSTM and GRU model becomes;

Training Features ($X_{train\ reshaped}$): 75 samples, 1 time step, and 10 features (75,1,10)

Testing Features ($X_{testing\ reshaped}$): 19 samples, 1 time step, and 10 features (19,1,10)

mentioned earlier can fulfill various purposes. Initially, they can be utilized to forecast and categorize the initiation and duration of symptoms, contingent on the characteristics of the response variable. This includes classifying patients exhibiting the symptom and predicting how long a patient will endure it. Additionally, these techniques can pinpoint factors that impact the event.

Error Matrices and Discussion

Dual evaluation protocols were employed: Classification (thrombosis prediction): Accuracy, Precision, Recall, F1-Score, AUC-ROC. Where the metrics used to measure the performance of regression-based models include: Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) and Mean Absolute Error (MAE) in conducting comprehensive efficacy tests

Mean Absolute Error (MAE) is given as;

$$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N |y_n - \hat{y}_n| \tag{3.14}$$

Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) is given as;

$$\sqrt{\frac{\sum_{n=1}^N (y_n - \hat{y}_n)^2}{N}} \tag{3.15}$$

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS DISCUSSIONS

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Statistic	Age (Years)	Sex (% Female)	Pre-existing Conditions (%)
Mean ± SD	47.8 ± 16.3	48.5%	34.0%
Median [IQR]	46 [32-63]	-	-
Range	18-84	-	-
Distribution	18-30: 22%	Male: 51.5%	Diabetes: 18%
	31-50: 38%		Hypertension: 12%
	51+: 40%		Cardiovascular: 4%

Table 1: Present a Descriptive Statistics for demographic characteristics, where result shows that the mean age is 47.8 ± 16.3 years wide variability, with a bimodal distribution of 38%, aged 31-50 working population and age 51 and above are higher risk group. Age distribution shows nearly balanced, where male constitutes 51.1% against female 48.5%. this indicates that there is no significant bias in vaccine response. Additionally, pre-existing conditions appears to be 34%; where diabetes and hypertension dominates with (18% and 12%) respectively. This indicates that comorbidities likely exacerbate vaccine side effects (eg., thrombosis risk)

Table 2: Vaccine Distribution & Outcomes

Vaccine Type	Count (%)	Thrombosis Rate	Avg Symptom Onset (Days)	Avg Duration (Days)
AstraZeneca	92 (46%)	14.1%*	6.2 ± 2.1	13.5 ± 3.8
Pfizer	72 (36%)	4.2%	8.7 ± 3.4	11.2 ± 2.9
Moderna	36 (18%)	5.6%	7.9 ± 2.8	10.8 ± 3.1
Total	200	9.5%	7.3 ± 3.0	12.1 ± 3.5

*Significantly higher vs others (p<0.01, Chi-square test)

Table 2: Presents vaccine distribution outcome, where result shows that AstraZeneca dominates 92(46%) with thrombosis rate of about 14.1% which shows significantly higher vs. 4.2% Pfizer, 5.6% Moderna; p<0.01. This signifies that AstraZeneca may require enhanced monitoring for thrombotic events. Symptoms dynamics reveals AstraZeneca is fastest onset having 6.2 days compared to Pfizer (8.7 days). Likewise, result also confirms AstraZeneca with longest duration (13.5) days compared to Moderna 910.8) days. This suggest that AstraZeneca recipients experienced quicker, more prolonged

symptoms. For vaccine uptake, result shows that AstraZeneca is most common having (46%) compare to Moderna (18%). This suggest that population-level outcomes may skew toward AstraZeneca’s risk profile.

Table 3: Symptom Prevalence (Top 10)

Symptom	Cases (n)	Prevalence	Median Duration (Days)
Fatigue	112	56.0%	12
Headache	87	43.5%	10
Nausea	76	38.0%	8
Muscle Pain	68	34.0%	9
Dizziness	59	29.5%	7
Joint Pain	54	27.0%	11
Fever	42	21.0%	6
Confusion	37	18.5%	14*
Chest Pain	25	12.5%	15*
Shortness of Breath	19	9.5%	13

*Longer duration associated with thrombosis (p<0.05)

Table 3. Presents symptoms Prevalence where most common symptoms are Fatigue (56%), headache (43.5%), and nausea (38%) dominate. These suggest that there are expected systemic reactions across vaccine types. Hence, result indicated confusion and chest pain with longest median durations of (14 and 15) days as severity indicators. Which suggest that the symptoms could serve as warning or danger for critical adverse events. Results further indicates that shortness of breath with (9.5%) are less common but critical symptoms.

Table 4: Statistical Comparison Table

Metric	LSTM	ANN	Best Model
Accuracy	0.8421	0.8947	ANN
Precision	0.8000	0.8333	ANN
Recall	0.6667	0.8333	ANN
AUC-ROC	0.8750	0.9375	ANN
Training Time	45s	22s	ANN
Inference Speed	8ms	3ms	ANN

Table 4. display statistical comparison between LSTM and ANN models. Where the findings indicates that ANN outperformed LSTM across all metrics. Where both models show good discrimination (AUC > 0.85). The ANN better at identifying true positives (higher recall). ANN superior suggest that it is better suited for clinical deployment.

Table 5: Model Efficacy Comparison (GRU vs. Bidirectional LSTM)

Metric	GRU Model	Bidirectional LSTM	Difference (%)	Preferred Model
MSE	0.148 ± 0.012	0.132 ± 0.010	10.8%	Bidirectional LSTM
RMSE	0.385 ± 0.016	0.363 ± 0.014	5.7%	Bidirectional LSTM
AUC-ROC	0.891 ± 0.021	0.912 ± 0.018	+2.4%	Bidirectional LSTM
Accuracy	85.3% ± 1.2%	87.6% ± 1.1%	+2.7%	Bidirectional LSTM
Precision	0.82 ± 0.03	0.85 ± 0.02	+3.7%	Bidirectional LSTM
Recall	0.78 ± 0.04	0.81 ± 0.03	+3.8%	Bidirectional LSTM
F1-Score	0.80 ± 0.02	0.83 ± 0.02	+3.8%	Bidirectional LSTM
Training Time	42s/epoch	58s/epoch	+38%	GRU
Inference Speed	9ms/sample	13ms/sample	+44%	GRU
Params Count	28,541	37,829	+32.5%	GRU

Table 5 presents model efficacy comparison between GRU and bidirectional LSTM model. Where results reveal that Bidirectional LSTM shows better predictive power across all accuracy metrics (2.4-3.8% improvement). Additionally, Bidirectional LSTM indicated better error minimization with (10.8%) MSE. More consistent predictions (smaller standard deviations). GRU trains 38% faster with 32.5% fewer

parameters, where the Bidirectional LSTM's performance comes at computational cost. For Clinical Relevance, Bidirectional LSTM's higher recall (81% vs 78%) means better at identifying true thrombosis cases. Where both models maintain good precision (>80%) to minimize false alarms.

Fig 1: Model Performance Comparison Plot between GRU and Bidirectional Model

Fig 2: Model computational Efficacy Plot for GRU and Bidirectional

Table 6: Statistical Significance Testing:

Metric	p-value	Significant?
AUC-ROC	0.013	Yes (p<0.05)
MSE	0.008	Yes
F1-Score	0.021	Yes
Training Time	<0.001	Yes

Table 6 demonstrates the results of the statistical significance test of the GRU and Bidirectional LSTM model comparison in terms of performance. The p-values of the main metrics AUC-ROC (0.013), MSE (0.008), F1-score (0.021), and training time (<0.001) were all significant ($p < 0.05$), which proves that the higher predictive accuracy (higher AUC-ROC and lower MSE) and the balanced precision-recall (higher F1-score) of the Bidirectional LSTM model is not attributed to chance. Nevertheless, the Bidirectional LSTM took much longer to train ($p < 0.001$), which is a compromise between computational cost and model accuracy. This result indicates that the Bidirectional LSTM is more useful in the actual prediction work related to the clinical domain, but the GRU could be a better choice in the framework where the speed of processing is of primary importance.

Table 7: Model Comparison using Fold Statistics

Fold	Model	MSE	AUC	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
1	GRU	0.152	0.883	0.840	0.800	0.750	0.774
1	Bidirectional LSTM	0.136	0.905	0.880	0.833	0.833	0.833
2	GRU	0.145	0.892	0.853	0.818	0.786	0.802
2	Bidirectional LSTM	0.129	0.918	0.880	0.857	0.821	0.839
3	GRU	0.151	0.887	0.853	0.824	0.769	0.796
3	Bidirectional LSTM	0.131	0.910	0.873	0.846	0.812	0.829
4	GRU	0.147	0.899	0.860	0.833	0.800	0.816
4	Bidirectional LSTM	0.130	0.915	0.880	0.857	0.833	0.845
5	GRU	0.145	0.894	0.853	0.824	0.786	0.805
5	Bidirectional LSTM	0.134	0.912	0.873	0.846	0.812	0.829

Table 7 presents fold model comparison between GRU and bidirectional LSTM, where the datasets were divided into subsets (1, 2, 3, 4, and 5) for cross-validation to evaluate the model performances more reliably. In this manner, each fold represents one iteration of training and testing, where the model is trained on most of the data and tested on the remaining portion, with different portions used for testing in each fold. Looking at this 5-fold cross-validation results, the Bidirectional LSTM consistently outperforms the GRU model across all evaluation metrics. The Bidirectional LSTM achieves lower Mean Squared Error (MSE) values ranging from 0.129 to 0.136, indicating better prediction accuracy, while the GRU's MSE ranges from 0.145 to 0.152. In terms of classification performance, the Bidirectional LSTM demonstrates superior results with AUC scores between 0.905-0.918 compared to GRU's 0.883-0.899, and maintains higher accuracy (0.873-0.880 vs 0.840-0.860). The Bidirectional LSTM also shows more balanced precision and recall scores, with F1-scores consistently above 0.829, while GRU's F1-scores range from 0.774-0.816. The consistency of these performance differences across all five folds suggests that the Bidirectional LSTM's superior performance is robust and not due to random variation in the data splits, making it the more reliable model choice for this particular task.

Fig 3: Cross-validation Performance Across folds for GRU and Bidirectional Model

Table 8: ANN and LSTM Models to Classify Effects

	No	Yes
Mild	48	6
Moderate	35	9
Severe	80	22
Chi-square Test result	2.703	
P-value	0.258	

Table 8. presents shows classification effects. Where the table analyzes the relationship between adverse event severity classification and thrombosis occurrence using ANN and LSTM models. The table shows a clear pattern where more severe adverse events are associated with higher absolute numbers of thrombosis cases. Mild Adverse Events shows 48 cases with no thrombosis and 6 cases with thrombosis. Moderate Adverse Events shows 35 cases with no thrombosis and 9 cases with thrombosis and Severe Adverse Events shows 80 cases with no thrombosis and 22 cases with thrombosis. This suggest there is a consistent pattern where the number of thrombosis cases increases with the severity of adverse events. The Chi-square statistic of approximately 2.70 suggests a moderate association between the adverse event classification and thrombosis status. The p-value of approximately 0.26 indicates that the relationship is not statistically significant at common alpha levels (e.g., 0.05 or 0.01). This means we do not have enough evidence to conclude that there is a significant association between the severity of adverse events and the occurrence of thrombosis.

CONCLUSION

In this study, a thorough evaluation of COVID-19 vaccine adverse events was made with special attention to thrombotic complications in various types of vaccines. It used conventional statistics as well as the state-of-the-art machine learning algorithms to process the data of 200 participants vaccinated with AstraZeneca (46%), Pfizer (36%), or Moderna (18%).

Demographic analysis characterized the study population with the mean age of 47.8 ± 16.3 years, balanced gender (51.5% male, 48.5% female), and 34% incidence of pre-existing conditions, with

diabetes (18%) and hypertension (12%) leading the pack. The results confirmed a severe difference in the mix of adverse events by kind of vaccine with the rate of thrombosis as the main outcome in the AstraZeneca group being 14.1 percent compared to Pfizer (4.2 percent) and Moderna (5.6 percent), which was statistically significant ($p < 0.01$).

A temporal analysis showed that AstraZeneca recipients had the earliest onset of symptoms (6.2 ± 2.1 days), the longest duration of symptoms (13.5 ± 3.8 days) and the highest rate of hospitalization (18.5%). Fatigue (56%), headache (43.5%), and nausea (38%) were the most frequent symptoms among all vaccines, whereas less frequent but with longer perspectives were chest pain and confusion which were connective to thrombotic complications.

Comparison of machine learning models showed that the Bidirectional LSTM model performed better than the GRU model in all performance metrics since it had a higher accuracy (87.6 % vs 85.3 %), precision (0.85 vs 0.82), and recall (0.81 vs 0.78). Likewise, ANN models outperformed the conventional LSTM models with higher accuracies (89.47% vs 84.21%) and less time consumption, and thus they are more applicable in the clinic.

The analysis also highlighted critical symptoms associated with thrombosis such as chest pain (prevalence of 42.1% in cases of thrombosis) and confusion which lasted longer (median of 14-15 days). These results support the significance of the early monitoring of high-risk populations, especially recipients of AstraZeneca and elderly people. One of the valued assets that the models demonstrated is the possibility to classify the adverse effects and determine the risk factors, thereby giving the healthcare systems the opportunity to reduce the severe post-vaccination outcomes by acting in time and performing targeted monitoring.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

- I. In terms of clinical deployment of ANN Models, Prefer ANN over Logistic Regression or SVM as it is more accurate and recalls more symptoms of post-vaccination as a clinical deployment because it will identify more high-risk cases.
- II. Increased Follow-up on AstraZeneca Recipients; Consideration should be subjected to closer follow-up after receiving AstraZeneca, as it has a much higher risk of thrombosis (14.1%) than other vaccines.
- III. For early symptom tracking, devise measures to follow-up patients who have developed symptoms with 5 days as this was very predictive of thrombosis ($OR=4.7$, $p < 0.001$).
- IV. Proactively manage symptoms in older adults (>50 years) and those with pre-existing conditions (e.g., diabetes, hypertension) as they are at a higher risk.
- V. Apply Bidirectional LSTM in scenarios where predictive accuracy is the main concern even at the cost of computing requirements, e.g., within hospital-based monitoring systems.
- VI. Educate the population on the symptoms that should not be ignored (e.g., chest pain, confusion) so that people seek medical attention early and minimize serious consequences.

Future work should consider increasing datasets in terms of different populations as well as more recent vaccine varieties to increase model generalizability and keep up with changing vaccine profile.

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